

ML2++ Tutorial for Evaluating IoT-Oriented Time-Series Workflows

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Abstract

ML2++ is a model-driven environment that integrates ThingML-based IoT architectures with automated machine-learning and time-series forecasting workflows. This tutorial is designed for evaluation experiments in which participants inspect a complete ML2++ model for a river-flow forecasting scenario, execute it in the ML2++ Quick-Start Editor, and then modify it to observe how changes affect code generation, runtime behavior, and plots. The example model combines three interacting ThingML components (`SensorClient`, `FlowServer`, and `FlowAnalytics`) with an MLP-based forecasting pipeline and automated visualization directives.

Figure 1: Overview of the TejoFlow process.

1 Introduction

ML2++ extends the ML2 and ML2+ lines of work by embedding data-analytics and time-series forecasting constructs directly into *ThingML-based* IoT models. Instead of manually writing *ThingML-generated Java* for IoT orchestration and separate *Python* scripts for data processing and learning, users specify datasets, preprocessing steps, forecasting models, evaluation metrics, and visualization directives in a high-level domain-specific language (DSL). From this specification, code generators produce a runnable implementation, including (i) IoT orchestration/communication code and (ii) analytics and plotting scripts.

For evaluation experiments, it is important that participants can: (i) understand a non-trivial ML2++ model, (ii) execute it in the ML2++ Quick-Start Editor (browser-based), and (iii) modify parameters and visualization options to observe the impact of their changes. Accordingly, this tutorial is structured in two main parts:

- **Part 1** explains the example ML2++ model used in this tutorial.
- **Part 2** guides participants through the ML2++ Quick-Start Editor and proposes small exercises that involve editing and re-running the model.

2 Part 1: Example ML2++ Model Instance

2.1 Scenario Overview

The tutorial is built around TejoFlow, a **daily discharge forecasting** scenario for the Tejo River, inspired by operational hydrology systems. The scenario uses a historical daily-discharge dataset spanning **1984–2023**. The goal of this scenario is to demonstrate how ML2++ combines IoT data streams, automated preprocessing, a forecasting model, and runtime decision logic within a single executable specification.

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The system consists of three interacting ThingML components (Figure 1):

- **SensorClient** simulates a monitoring node that produces three daily discharge streams:
 - daily average river discharge at *Albufeira do Fratel*,
 - daily average river discharge at *Albufeira de Castelo de Bode*,
 - daily average river discharge at the target station *Almourol*.

It sends these values to the server.

- **FlowServer** acts as a lightweight middleware component that receives sensor data, forwards the values to the

analytics component, and returns either:

- an *acknowledgement* (safe condition), or
 - an *alert* (when the predicted flow exceeds a threshold).
- **FlowAnalytics** performs the machine-learning pipeline, including:
 - loading and preprocessing the time-series dataset,
 - training an MLP-based forecasting model,
 - predicting the next three future flow values,
 - checking whether predictions exceed a risk threshold, and
 - returning `safe()` or `alert()` messages.

Overall, this scenario forms an integrated IoT-ML workflow that illustrates how ML2++ automatically generates both IoT orchestration/communication logic (ThingML-generated Java code) and the corresponding machine-learning logic (Python scripts) from a single high-level model.

Reference tables. Appendix A provides Table 2, which summarizes the main ML2++ `data_analytics` directives, and Table 3, which summarizes the core ThingML syntax used in the scenario.

2.2 Complete Model Listing

The complete ML2++ model instance used in this tutorial is provided in Appendix A (see Listing 2). The listing includes (i) the ThingML components (`SensorClient`, `FlowServer`, and `FlowAnalytics`), (ii) message definitions used for communication, and (iii) the `data_analytics` configuration that specifies the dataset, preprocessing, time-series setup, forecasting model, evaluation metrics, and visualization directives.

2.3 Model Structure

The model starts with datatype declarations that map to C, Java, and JavaScript types, ensuring that the generated code is type-consistent across supported backends. The `FlowMsgs` fragment defines all messages exchanged in the system. At the IoT level, `SensorClient` sends `sensor_data` and waits for an `ack`, while `FlowServer` forwards the data to `FlowAnalytics` and returns an `ack` with a contextual status (`safe` or `alert`).

`FlowAnalytics` contains both structural properties and the `data_analytics` block `da1`, which specifies the dataset, preprocessing configuration, time-series setup, forecasting model, evaluation, and visualization. Its behavior is encoded as a ThingML statechart; however, in this tutorial it is best understood as a set of *workflow tasks* that orchestrate the ML pipeline rather than as a classical reactive control state machine. Concretely, the workflow (i) performs preprocessing and training once during initialization and then (ii) reacts

to incoming `query` messages by calling `da_predict`, storing prediction results, and sending either `safe` or `alert` depending on whether the forecast exceeds the configured threshold.

3 Part 2: Quick-Start Editor Tasks

3.1 Opening the Editor and Logging In

This part is organized as a set of user **tasks** performed in the ML2++ Quick-Start Editor.

Task 2.4.1: Open the editor. Open the ML2++ Quick-Start Editor using the URL provided by the instructor (e.g., shared by email or on the session handout): `https://ml2plusplus.jvmhost.net/`.

Task 2.4.2: Log in. Log in using the credentials provided by the instructor *before the session* (or at the beginning of the session). Example credentials:

- **Username:** `user1` **Password:** `password1`

If these do not work, use the alternative login:

- **Username:** `user2` **Password:** `password2`

Task 2.4.3: Identify the workspace elements. After logging in, the *Workspace* page contains:

- a **Model Editor** text area,
- action buttons: **Save Model**, **Show Preprocessing Plot**, **Generate Code**, **Download Code**, **Run Code**, and **Show Forecasting Plots**,
- a **Console Output** panel at the bottom of the page (logs from preprocessing, code generation, and execution).

Task 2.4.4 (Optional): Show preprocessing plot. Click **Show Preprocessing Plot** to run the preprocessing script and visualize the resampled time series. Progress and log messages appear in **Console Output**.

Task 2.4.5: Generate code. Click **Generate Code** to generate executable artifacts, including: (i) ThingML-generated **Java** code for IoT orchestration/communication and (ii) **Python** scripts for data analytics (preprocessing, training, prediction, and plotting).

Task 2.4.6 (Optional): Download code. Click **Download Code** to obtain a `.zip` archive containing the generated files. Appendix B summarizes how to run the generated project locally.

3.2 Loading the Sample Model

Task 2.5.1: Clear the editor. In the **Model Editor**, delete any existing content.

Task 2.5.2: Paste the sample model. Copy the complete model (Listing 2) into the **Model Editor**. From this point onward, all actions affect this specific model instance.

3.3 Saving, Generating, and Running

Task 2.6.1: Save the model. Click **Save Model**. A confirmation message should appear.

Task 2.6.2: Generate code. Click **Generate Code**. Confirm in **Console Output** that generation finished successfully.

Task 2.6.3: Run code. Click **Run Code**. Inspect **Console Output** to follow preprocessing, training, prediction, and decision outputs (`safe()` / `alert()`).

Task 2.6.4: Show forecasting plots. Click **Show Forecasting Plots** to visualize forecasting outputs configured in the `model` block.

3.4 Exercise 1: Modifying Model Parameters

In this exercise, participants modify forecasting parameters directly in the ML2++ model and observe how the generated pipeline changes after re-execution (without manually editing Python code).

3.4.1 Locating the Model Block

The `model` block of `dal` is shown in the full model listing (Listing 2). For convenience, the relevant fragment is repeated in Listing 1.

```
model {
  autoML OFF
  algorithm MLP mymlp(
    hidden_layer_sizes (90,90),
    input_activation relu,
    hidden_activation relu,
    output_activation relu,
    regularization 12,
    dropout 0.2,
    optimizer adam,
    rate 0.001,
    batch_size 32,
    epochs 100,

    early_stopping disable,
    overfitting_Plots TRAINING_LOSS,
    forecasting_plots FORECAST_VS_ACTUAL
  )
  training_results "data/training.txt"
}
```

Parameter	Meaning / effect
<code>hidden_layer_sizes</code>	Neurons per hidden layer (e.g., (90,90) = two layers). Larger may increase capacity and training time.
<code>dropout</code>	Dropout rate (e.g., 0.2). Higher reduces overfitting but may underfit.
<code>regularization</code>	Weight regularization type (e.g., 12).
<code>optimizer</code>	Optimizer (e.g., adam).
<code>rate</code>	Learning rate. Too high may diverge; too low may train slowly.
<code>batch_size</code>	Samples per gradient update. Affects stability and speed.
<code>epochs</code>	Training epochs. More increases time and may overfit.
<code>early_stopping</code>	Stop early if validation does not improve (if enabled).
<code>overfitting_Plots</code>	Training/validation diagnostic plots (e.g., loss curves).
<code>forecasting_plots</code>	Forecast plots (e.g., forecast vs actual).

Table 1: Quick reference for selected `model` parameters used in the tutorial.

Listing 1: MLP model block in `dal`.

When you use **Download Code** and run the generated project locally, you can find it under the project `data/` directory (or the configured output directory).

Parameter quick reference. Table 1 summarizes the meaning of the most relevant model parameters used in the exercise.

3.4.2 Editing and Re-running

Important. Keep attributes in the grammar-defined order; otherwise, the generator may map values to the wrong fields.

ML2++ blocks (e.g., `preprocessing`, `time_series`, `model`, `evaluation`, and `visualization`) accept only specific parameters. The Quick-Start Editor supports this via **auto-completion**.

Using auto-completion (Ctrl+Space).

1. Place the cursor **inside the block** you want to edit (e.g., inside `model{...}`).
2. Press **Ctrl+Space**.
3. Select one of the suggested parameters (e.g., `epochs`, `batch_size`, `dropout`, `hidden_layer_sizes`, `forecasting_plots`).
4. Enter the desired value and save the model (Figure 2).

Task 2.7.1 (Model parameter change). Using Ctrl+Space, edit the `model` block to (i) switch the forecasting algorithm and (ii) change one training parameter. For example:

- switch from `algorithm MLP ...` to `algorithm LSTM ...` (selectable via Ctrl+Space),

Figure 2: Using Ctrl+Space in the ML2++ Quick-Start Editor to display valid parameters inside a block (example shown for the model block).

- add `return_sequences true` immediately after the hidden-layer definition (e.g., after `hidden_layer_sizes`),
- reduce epochs (e.g., $100 \rightarrow 10$).

Then re-run the workflow:

1. click **Save Model**,
2. click **Generate Code**,
3. click **Run Code**,
4. click **Show Forecasting Plots**.

Note how training time and the generated learning/forecasting curves change.

Task 2.7.2 (Visualization change: preprocessing plots). In the visualization block, add one extra preprocessing plot using Ctrl+Space. For example, extend the plot set from a single line plot to include a histogram:

```
visualization {
  plots LINE_PLOT, HISTOGRAM
}
```

Re-run the same workflow (Save → Generate Code → Run Code). In the web editor, plots are shown via the plotting buttons. When executing the downloaded project locally, the generated figures are saved under a `plots/` (or similarly named) output folder.

Where to configure plots.

- **Preprocessing plots** are configured in the visualization block (e.g., `LINE_PLOT`, `HISTOGRAM`).
- **Overfitting and forecasting plots** are configured in the model block (e.g., `overfitting_Plots`, `TRAINING_LOSS`, `forecasting_plots`, `FORECAST_VS_ACTUAL`).

References

Z. Mardani Korani, G. V. Jesus, E. Alves, and A. Oliveira. ML2++: A Model-Driven Blended Framework for Automated Machine Learning, Time Series Forecasting, and Data Visualization in IoT Applications. In *Proceedings of the MODELS 2025 Conference (to appear)*, 2025.

Z. Mardani Korani, G. V. Jesus, E. Alves, and A. Oliveira. From ML2 to ML2+: Integrating Time Series Forecasting in Model-Driven Engineering of Smart IoT Applications. In *Proceedings of the MBSE-AI Integration Workshop*, 2025.

A Full ML2++ Model Instance

```
datatype String<256>
@type_checker "String"
@c_type "char*"
@java_type "String"
@js_type "String"

datatype Boolean<1>
@type_checker "Boolean"
@c_type "uint8_t"
@java_type "boolean"
@js_type "boolean"

datatype Int32<4>
@type_checker "Integer"
@c_type "int32_t"
@java_type "int"
@js_type "int"

thing fragment FlowMsgs {
  // Daily discharge values (m3/s): inputs =
  // Fratel + Castelo de Bode, target =
  // Almourol
  message sensor_data(fratel_discharge :
    Int32, castelo_bode_discharge : Int32,
    almourol_discharge : Int32)
  message ack()
  message query(fratel_discharge : Int32,
    castelo_bode_discharge : Int32,
    almourol_discharge : Int32)
  message alert()
  message safe()
}

thing SensorClient includes FlowMsgs {
  required port data_service {
    sends sensor_data receives ack
  }

  // Simulated discharge values (replace
  // with real readings in a real deployment)
  property my_fratel_discharge : Int32 = 100
  property my_castelo_bode_discharge : Int32
    = 120
  property my_almourol_discharge : Int32 =
    110

  statechart SensorClientBehavior init
  SendData {
    state SendData {
      on entry do
        print
          "\n===== \n"
```

```
        print "SensorClient started (DAILY
cycle)\n"
        print "In Quick-Start, the daily
schedule is external.\n"
        print
          "===== \n"
        print "Sending discharge packet
(Fratel, Castelo de Bode, Almourol)... \n"

data_service!sensor_data(my_fratel_discharge,
my_castelo_bode_discharge,
my_almourol_discharge)
end
transition -> ReceiveAck
event data_service?ack
}

state ReceiveAck {
  on entry do
    print "ACK received from server.
Packet delivered.\n"
end
transition -> Stop
}

state Stop {
  on entry print "SensorClient
finished.\n"
}
}

thing FlowServer includes FlowMsgs {
  provided port data_service {
    sends ack receives sensor_data
  }

  required port fa_service {
    sends query receives alert receives safe
  }

  property fratel_discharge : Int32
  property castelo_bode_discharge : Int32
  property almourol_discharge : Int32

  statechart FlowServerBehavior init GetData
  {
    state GetData {
      internal
      event e : data_service?sensor_data
      action do
        fratel_discharge = e.fratel_discharge
        castelo_bode_discharge =
e.castelo_bode_discharge
        almourol_discharge =
e.almourol_discharge
        print "Received packet. Forwarding
to FlowAnalytics... \n"
        fa_service!query(fratel_discharge,
castelo_bode_discharge,
almourol_discharge)
end
```

```

    transition -> Ack
    event fa_service?safe
    transition -> Alert
    event fa_service?alert
  }

  state Ack {
    on entry do
      print "SAFE. Sending ACK back to
SensorClient.\n"
      data_service!ack()
    end
    transition -> GetData
  }

  state Alert {
    on entry do
      print "ALERT. Sending ACK back to
SensorClient.\n"
      data_service!ack()
    end
    transition -> GetData
  }
}

thing FlowAnalytics includes FlowMsgs {
  provided port fa_service {
    sends alert sends safe receives query
  }

  // Latest inputs from server
  property fratel_discharge : Int32
  property castelo_bode_discharge : Int32
  property almourol_discharge : Int32

  // 3-step prediction outputs (t+1, t+2,
t+3)
  property predction1 : Int32
  property predction2 : Int32
  property predction3 : Int32

  data_analytics da1 @dalib
  "keras-tensorflow" {
    data {
      dataset "usecase1.csv" // Hosted on
the ML2++ platform: Tejo River daily
discharge dataset (1984/2023), used for
training + prediction
      labels ON // CSV contains a header row
(column names)
      features fratel_discharge, // Input
feature 1: discharge at Albufeira do
Fratel
          castelo_bode_discharge, //
Input feature 2: discharge at Albufeira
de Castelo de Bode
          almourol_discharge // Feature
3: discharge at Almourol (also used as
the target below)
      output_features almourol_discharge //
Prediction target (dependent variable):

```

```

Almourol discharge
  timestamps ON // Dataset includes a
timestamp column (used as time index for
resampling/ordering)
  common_period_threshold 10 // Align
multiple series; keep only periods where
at least 10 common time points exist
}

preprocessing {
  resample DAILY // Force daily
frequency (fill/align to one value per
day before supervised conversion)
}

time_series {
  sequential TRUE // Treat data as
sequences (required for time-series
windowing)
  steps 3 // Forecast horizon: predict
next 3 days (t+1, t+2, t+3)
  lag 20 // Input window size: use the
past 20 days as model input
  multivariate ON // Use multiple input
features jointly (Fratel + Castelo +
past Almourol)
  supervised_learning ON // Convert the
time series into supervised (X,y) using
sliding windows
}

model {
  autoML OFF // Do not search
automatically; use the explicit manual
configuration below
  algorithm MLP mlp_model(
    hidden_layer_sizes (90,90), //
Architecture: 2 hidden layers with 90
neurons each
    input_activation relu, // Activation
used at the input layer
    hidden_activation relu, //
Activation used in hidden layers
    output_activation relu, //
Activation used at output layer
    regularization 'l2', // L2 weight
regularization
    dropout 0.2, // Dropout probability
(regularization)
    optimizer adam, // Optimizer used
for training
    rate 0.001, // Learning rate for the
optimizer
    batch_size 32, // Batch size
(samples per gradient update)
    epochs 20, // Number of training
epochs
    early_stopping 'disable', // Disable
early stopping
    overfitting_plots TRAINING_LOSS, //
Generate training-loss curve

```

```

    forecasting_plots FORECAST_VS_ACTUAL
    // Generate forecast vs. actual plot
    )
    training_results "data/training.txt"
    // File path where training log/metrics
    are stored after training completes
    }

    evaluation {
        prediction_results prediction1,
        prediction2, prediction3 // Output
        properties that store the 3 forecasted
        values
        metrics MSE // Evaluation metric to
        compute
    }

    visualization {
        plots LINE_PLOT // Preprocessing
        visualization: line plot of the
        resampled time series
    }
}

statechart FlowAnalyticsBehavior init
Preprocess {
    state Preprocess {
        on entry do
            print "Preprocessing: resample DAILY
+ lag/steps + supervised conversion...\n"
            da_preprocess dal
        end
        transition -> Train
    }

    state Train {
        on entry do
            print "Training MLP model...\n"
            da_train dal
        end
        transition -> Ready
    }

    state Ready {
        on entry print "Ready for prediction
requests.\n"
        transition -> Predict
        event m : fa_service?query
        action do
            fratel_discharge = m.fratel_discharge
            castelo_bode_discharge =
m.castelo_bode_discharge
            almourol_discharge =
m.almourol_discharge
        end
    }

    state Predict {
        on entry do
            print "Predicting next 3 days for
Almourol...\n"

```

```

        da_predict dal (fratel_discharge,
        castelo_bode_discharge,
        almourol_discharge)
        end
        transition -> Decide
        on exit da_save dal
    }

    state Decide {
        on entry do
            print "Decision: checking flood
threshold (150 m3/s)...\n"
            if (prediction1 >= 150 or prediction2
            >= 150 or prediction3 >= 150)
                fa_service!alert()
            else
                fa_service!safe()
            end
        transition -> Ready
    }
}

configuration RiverFlowCfg @compiler
    "python_java" {
        instance sensorClient : SensorClient
        instance flowServer : FlowServer
        instance flowAnalytics : FlowAnalytics

        connector sensorClient.data_service =>
            flowServer.data_service
        connector flowServer.fa_service =>
            flowAnalytics.fa_service
    }
}

```

Listing 2: Complete ML2++ model instance used in the tutorial.

B Local Execution (Optional)

After clicking **Download Code** and extracting the ZIP archive:

- Go to the generated project directory (e.g., `python_java/`).
- Build: `mvn clean install`
- Run the fat JAR from `target/`: `java -jar <jarname>.jar`
- Ensure the dataset is available at the configured path (e.g., `data/usecase1.csv`), or update the dataset `"..."` directive in the model before generating/downloading again.

Table 2: ML2++ Data Analytics Block – Detailed Description of All Directives
Important. Keep attributes in the DSL (grammar-defined) order; otherwise, the generator may map values to the wrong fields.

Block / Feature	Description
<i>Data section</i>	
dataset	Mandatory. Path to the time-series dataset file used for training and prediction.
labels	Optional. Indicates presence of a header/labels (ON, OFF, SEMI).
features	Optional. List of input features (independent variables).
input_features	Optional. Explicit list of model inputs (if different from features).
output_features	Optional. Target feature(s) to predict (dependent variables).
timestamps	Optional. Whether the dataset contains an explicit time index.
common_period_threshold	Optional. Threshold for aligning multiple time series to a common time period.
<i>Preprocessing section</i>	
preprocess_feature_scaler	Optional. Scaling strategy (e.g., StandardScaler, MinMaxScaler).
preprocess_sample_normalizer	Optional. Sample normalization strategy (e.g., L2, L1, max norm).
fill_missing	Optional. Missing-value handling (e.g., forward fill, interpolation, mean).
remove_outliers	Optional. Enables/disables outlier removal procedures.
advanced_imputation	Optional. Enables advanced/model-based imputation of missing data.
lag_features	Optional. Creates lagged versions of features as additional inputs.
rolling_window	Optional. Rolling-window statistics (e.g., moving average, rolling std).
resample	Optional. Resampling frequency (e.g., MINUTELY, HOURLY, DAILY).
transformations	Optional. Higher-level transformations (e.g., log transform, differencing, smoothing).
<i>Time-series and supervised-learning section</i>	
sequential	Optional. Treat input as sequential/time series.
steps	Optional. Number of future steps to predict.
lag	Optional. Past window size (number of lagged steps).
multivariate	Optional. Enable multivariate modeling with multiple inputs.
stationary_check	Optional. Enable stationarity tests and diagnostics.
seasonality_detection	Optional. Automatic seasonality detection (e.g., Fourier or moving-average based).
supervised_learning	Optional. Construct supervised dataset (X, y).
create_lagged_features	Optional. Explicit flag to generate lagged features in supervised dataset.
sliding_window	Optional. Sliding-window strategy for building input–output pairs.
<i>Model section</i>	
autoML	Optional. Enable/disable automated model/parameter selection.
algorithm	Mandatory. Algorithm to use (e.g., MLP, LSTM, ARIMA).
training_results	Optional. File path where training logs/metrics are stored after training completes (e.g., "data/training.txt").
hyperparameter_tuning	Optional. Hyperparameter search strategy (grid/random/Bayesian).
ensemble_methods	Optional. Ensemble method (bagging/boosting/stacking).
<i>Evaluation and analysis section</i>	
prediction_results	Optional. Model properties storing prediction outputs (e.g., 3-step forecasts).
metrics	Optional. Metrics (e.g., RMSE, MAE, MSE, R_SQUARED).
outlier_detection	Optional. Post-hoc outlier detection on predictions/residuals.
clustering	Optional. Time-series clustering/grouping analysis.
context	Optional. Application context declaration.
<i>Visualization section</i>	
plots	Optional. List of plots to generate (preprocessing and/or forecasting plots).

Table 3: ThingML Syntax Commands

Command/Keyword	Purpose	Example
thing	Declare a Thing/component	<code>thing SensorClient { ... }</code>
thing fragment	Reusable message fragment	<code>thing fragment FlowMsgs { ... }</code>
message	Define message	<code>message sensor_data(...)</code>
provided port	Declare provided port	<code>provided port fa_service { ... }</code>
required port	Declare required port	<code>required port data_service { ... }</code>
property	Internal variable	<code>property x : Int32 = 10</code>
statechart	Define behavior	<code>statechart Behavior init S { ... }</code>
state	Declare state	<code>state Predict { on entry do ... end }</code>
on entry do ... end	Actions on entering a state	<code>on entry do da_train dal end</code>
transition → State	Transition to another state	<code>transition -> Ready</code>
transition ... event port?msg	Transition on message event	<code>transition -> Predict event fa_service?query</code>
internal event e: port?msg	Capture incoming message	<code>internal event e : data_service?sensor_data</code>
action do ... end	Execute multiple actions	<code>action do x = e.value end</code>
if (cond) ... else ...	Conditional execution	<code>if (p1 >= 150) fa_service!alert() else fa_service!safe()</code>
stop	Stop state machine	<code>stop</code>
connector	Connect ports	<code>connector A.p => B.p</code>
instance	Instantiate a Thing	<code>instance flowServer : FlowServer</code>
da_preprocess	Trigger preprocessing	<code>on entry do da_preprocess dal end</code>
da_train	Trigger training	<code>on entry do da_train dal end</code>
da_predict	Trigger prediction	<code>on entry do da_predict dal(...) end</code>
da_save	Save model state	<code>on exit do da_save dal end</code>